

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATION

In this article we will briefly focus on the advantages of maximum use of modern technologies during the lesson. Learning a Modern Foreign Language supports an understanding of living in a multi-cultural society, provides an opening to other cultures and fosters curiosity about the wider world. The benefits of using educational technology also include the improvement of learners' mental and physical health. By using these tools, students are able to enhance their learning and their cognitive skills, which in turn helps them improve their academic performance as well as their physical health.

Key words. *Modern technologies, teaching process, learning skills, interactive whiteboards, practice, success, traditional learning*

The last years increasingly raised the issue of using modern technologies in the educational process. It is not only new technical means, but also a new forms and methods of teaching, new approach to learning. The main goal that we set for ourselves, using modern technologies in learning a foreign language it's to show how technology can be effectively used to improve the quality of teaching foreign language students, the formation and development of their communicative culture, learning the practical mastery of a foreign language.

This paper aims to highlight the role of using modern technology in teaching English as a second language. It discusses different approaches and techniques which can assist English language students to improve their learning skills by using technology. The rapidly advancing age of technology has made it possible to overcome many different challenges in our world today. But the benefits and versatility of

technology are not as evident as it is with learning English. This is why more advocates support the integration of technology into education. The positive influence of technology when learning English is valuable and can maximize the overall experience. As technology becomes a major part in today's world, students can have more freedom and support to fully absorb the material. More students are choosing to learn English online because of the increased efficiency with lower costs. Technology and learning English go hand in hand and here are some reasons why more prefer online lessons. The biggest reason for incorporating technology into education is the overall changes in global communication. What was once inaccessible can now be easily reached by way of the internet. Technology opens doors to many more opportunities by linking the world together. The olden days of limited options for education are long gone and all thanks to technological advances. Students will not only have flexibility with online schooling but also have access to more resources.

Virtual Community of Learners; A pivotal aspect of learning English is to how to communicate with others in a social setting. Though it may seem impossible with online learning, the fact is exactly the opposite. Students now have a virtual community of learners to discuss topics with, seek advice, or gain leadership skills by helping others. Interactive whiteboards for instance, are a simple but invaluable way for English learners to access helpful resources or lessons. Instructors may include previous topics that are extremely important to progress to the next level. In addition, interactive whiteboards help a great deal to support an online education and are a perfect example of how to incorporate technology and learning English.

Another benefit of mixing technology and learning English is the possibility of heightening interest. A traditional classroom setting is often not conducive to learning because the rote strategies do not challenge or interest students. But technology has completely changed the game and makes it easier for English learners to focus because the content can be presented in a number of ways. Lessons that include computer-based instruction, visual aids, and technologically advanced materials help students achieve more in less time.

Conclusion

In conclusion, technology is certainly not beneficial only for education of because just about everything has become more accessible nowadays. But especially for learning English, having technical assistance and more flexibility Is the key to success. Traditional learning in a classroom is extremely limited and can only be ongoing as long as students are present. However, technology and learning English has allowed students to use mobile phones or computers for example, to access require information anytime they need. This not only helps students to absorb the material but also offers valuable practice on the proper ways to use tools of technology. Computers are regarded as an important instructional instrument in language classes in which teachers have convenient access, are sufficiently prepared and have some freedom in the curriculum. Computer technology is regarded by a lot of teachers to be a significant part of providing a high - quality education. Teachers should encourage learners to find appropriate activities through using computer technology in order to be successful in language learning. The use of suitable technological materials can be useful for all types of learners.

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